

ENHANCING THE IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY OF YOUTH IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION – A GUARANTEE OF SOCIETY’S DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article analyzes the ideological influences exerted on the consciousness of youth in the context of globalization, their role in social life, and the relevance of forming ideological immunity during this process. Alien ideas, mass culture, and information attacks accompanying globalization impact the worldview, values, and national identity of the younger generation. Therefore, protecting youth from ideological threats, educating them on a solid ideological foundation, and developing their critical thinking skills are considered among the most important tasks of today. The article highlights the significance of the education system, mass media, family, and state policy in this regard. It substantiates the thesis that strengthening ideological immunity is the main guarantee of social stability and development.

Keywords: globalization, threat, spiritual threat, ideological immunity, idea, innovation, stability.

The positive transformations occurring in our country across various spheres and the observed growth in mutual understanding and interethnic harmony, as well as the provision of religious tolerance, are primarily the results of ensuring peace. Today’s time demands the nurturing of youth with a sense of belonging to the Motherland, instilling loyalty, national pride, and self-respect, fostering them as dedicated, people-oriented, socially active individuals who live as patriots devoted to the development of their homeland. Indeed, love for the Motherland begins with the realization and deep understanding of national identity. In this regard, educational programs have been developed and implemented into the national education system, and the subject “The Idea of National Independence” has been introduced as part of the curriculum in general education schools.

In the current era of globalization, preserving love for the Motherland and national identity in youth upbringing has become a pressing issue. Social and humanitarian sciences play a crucial role in forming these feelings. Especially during the years of independence, significant attention has been paid to the subject of national idea in our country. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, stated in his Address to the Oliy Majlis on December 28, 2018:

“...To implement the immense tasks ahead of us, we need to develop a national idea that will serve as a source of strength and power for us. We must recognize our national identity, study the ancient and rich history of our homeland, enhance research efforts in this area, and comprehensively support the activities of scholars in the humanitarian field.”

The subject “The Idea of National Independence” primarily contributes to fostering patriotism among the youth. Understanding national identity begins with a person realizing who they are, what nation they belong to, knowing their history, and studying the heritage of their ancestors—in this process, the subject of national idea plays a significant role. Great attention is paid in our country to the education and upbringing of youth. To educate youth comprehensively and in line with modern requirements, leveraging foreign experiences and contemporary achievements of global science and innovative ideas, the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established based on the Presidential Decree №PF-5264 of November 29, 2017.

In the field of implementing innovations into social development, the main tasks have been defined as supporting the introduction of innovations in the education system, including modern, interactive, and creative teaching methods, and developing innovative educational programs that provide for extensive use of digital technologies. Supporting innovative technologies is necessary for teaching all subjects, including the subject of national idea, in order to organize lessons for youth that meet contemporary requirements. After all, youth are the future of the nation.

Educating each new generation as responsible and determined individuals who value independence and freedom, develop noble human qualities, and grow into dedicated patriots of the nation is the demand of our time. In the sustainable development of our country, the high spirituality and ideological immunity of our citizens hold significant importance. Spirituality and the national idea are key criteria determining the progress of society, the flourishing of the nation, and the perfection of the individual.

Subjects such as “Fundamentals of Spirituality,” “Cultural Studies,” and “National Idea: Basic Concepts and Principles” cultivate intellectuality, holistic development, and moral integrity among students, fostering a scientific worldview based on broad humanistic principles such as national peace, progress of the homeland, public welfare, social cooperation, interethnic harmony, and religious tolerance. Organizing lessons based on innovative technologies contributes further to the development of students’ worldview.

As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of Uzbekistan emphasized:

“There is a wise saying among our people: ‘Education and upbringing begin from the cradle.’ Only enlightenment leads a person to perfection and society to progress. Therefore, the state policy in the field of education must be based on the principle of lifelong learning, starting from kindergarten and continuing throughout life.”

Innovative technologies do not arise on their own; they require the integration of traditional teaching methods with modern pedagogical technologies. As time and society progress, it is essential to continuously improve educational processes to meet contemporary demands, which will yield positive results in the future.

In our country, significant attention is paid not only by the population but also by the government to raising the spiritual level of youth. On May 3, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, adopted Resolution №PQ-4307 “On Additional Measures to Improve the Effectiveness of Spiritual and Educational Work.” Special attention is given to fostering a harmoniously developed generation endowed with intellectual potential, consciousness, worldview, ideological immunity, and living with a sense of patriotism, love, and devotion to the people.

At the same time, in the modern world where ideological and ideological struggles are intensifying and spiritual threats are increasing, cases of indifference among youth towards national values, susceptibility to harmful alien ideas, and accidental involvement in criminal and extremist activities continue to occur.

This resolution outlines the following tasks: fostering active civic engagement among the population; promoting democratic principles in society based on national and universal values; effectively communicating the essence and content of ongoing political, economic, social, and spiritual-educational reforms and adopted legislative acts to the public; studying and improving the socio-spiritual environment in families, mahallas (local communities), educational institutions, and labor collectives; creating a socio-spiritual environment map of regions based on the principle “mahalla — district — region — republic,” and widely introducing modern information and communication technologies into this process; organizing continuous spiritual and educational work and advocacy in society based on the idea “Enlightenment against Ignorance,” developing effective, creative, and innovative methods in this direction; and conducting effective propaganda work against various internal

and external threats endangering peace, stability, sustainable development of our country, values, traditions, and humanitarian ideals.

In order to instill in youth a sense of belonging to the homeland and protect them from various alien ideas, it is necessary to use innovative teaching methods in the subject of national idea.

The tasks of educating youth in the spirit of national independence constitute a continuous and consistent educational process. The changing global ideological landscape requires further development of national ideological methods and approaches. Especially under the rapidly changing and accelerating pace of life in today's globalization, it is increasingly important to prevent spiritual emptiness in the minds of youth, instilling in their hearts and consciousness a healthy worldview and feelings of pride and respect for the heritage of their ancestors.

Simultaneously, one of today's pressing issues is for every individual to recognize the value of peaceful, calm, and prosperous life in our homeland and contribute their share toward strengthening this peaceful environment, feeling a deep personal connection to the fate and future of the nation. Forming a healthy worldview among youth is one of the essential conditions for nurturing a well-rounded generation. In this regard, resolving issues related to strengthening the spiritual and educational foundations of a worldview free from false and one-sided interpretations has practical and vital significance. In addressing this issue, the creative works and invaluable scientific and educational heritage left by the great scholars of our country in various fields of science hold exceptional importance.

From this perspective, the present research aims to analyze ideological processes taking place at the national, regional, and global levels, based on the experience of civil society and the cultural development of independent Uzbekistan. It is also essential to demonstrate the historical-philosophical and spiritual-educational significance of the scientific and spiritual heritage created by our ancestors in building a democratic, legal state and civil society.

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